

The Matrix of Human Resources Development Factors in Small and Medium Enterprises of Local Wisdom Products In Palembang

Zaleha Trihandayani¹, Fadhil Yamaly²

*Management Study Program, Faculty of Economics & Business, Muhammadiyah University Palembang Jl.
Jend. A.Yani 13 ULU, Palembang South Sumatra, Indonesia*

Abstract: All this time, the local wisdom product employees in Palembang were only directed to be able to work from skills that were owned informally and were handed down from generation to generation so that the ability to work for their employees was still simple or traditional, even though a small portion had penetrated into international markets, such as songket which was in demand in allied countries, for example: Malaysia and Brunei Darussalam. Pempekdankerupukkemplangthat had been sold in neighboring countries, while carving cabinets had not entered the international market. The factor matrix of human resource development in small and medium enterprises of local wisdom products in Palembang aimed to improve the knowledge, skills, and emotional intelligence of employees of small and medium businesses of local wisdom products in Palembang. For example: kerupukkemplang from Taiwanese were superior in the international market than kerupukkemplang from Palembang, it was expected that the local wisdom products in Palembang would still not be left behind despite having entered various similar products from outside the region and even outside the country. The research design used in conclusive design that was specifically descriptive with purposive sampling method. It was expected that the local wisdom products in Palembang could continue to survive and even be able to compete with similar products from domestic and abroad. This research was part of a dissertation of intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence and employee empowerment of job satisfaction and loyalty employees of small and medium enterprises local wisdom products in Palembang. The continuation of this dissertation was a research model of the strategy of challenging human resources in small and medium enterprises of local wisdom products in Palembang.

Keywords: Matrix of human resource development factors, small and medium enterprises.

I. INTRODUCTION

The existence of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) is realized so much when looking at the economic resilience of SMEs that are so large in several parts of the world. According to a study conducted by HSBC in May 2008 on SME business behavior that was taken the samples from 10 Asia Pacific countries said that economic uncertainty did not affect their decision to invest regionally. The development of investment behavior such as the recruitment of new employees, expanding investment to business partners namely world

trade and China is carried out by SMEs, especially in Bangladesh, Indonesia, India and Vietnam (Purwidianti, 2015).

The opening of opportunities for business people to participate in advancing the economy can be seen through the size of market activity in the area, in addition to the weak regional economic structure if not supported by the strength of the structure of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The middle and lower layers of the foundation in the structure of the regional economy so that Hollow Middle does not occur (vacancies in the middle) are medium and large enterprises that are not supported by small and medium enterprises because of economic shocks both nationally and internationally.

Human resource development in small and medium enterprises in the typical regional products in Palembang cannot only rely on the ability of the existing workforce so far, but the improvement of quality human resources, the creation of the latest technology and methods and human resource competencies to innovate in the development of SMEs. According to Zuhail (Cabinet Session, April 3rd, 2013) it is time to change the shallow investment paradigm with the exploitation of natural resources, minimum value added and cheap human resources or what is called natural resource driven economy into deep investment with the exploitation of knowledge, maximum technology transfer, and skillful and educated work forces or called innovation driven economy.

The progress of Palembang as a Metropolitan City makes Palembang must be ready to become one of the destinations for trade for economic players both domestic and foreign countries. Business capabilities must continue to be improved, especially for workers who come from Palembang, where the majority of them are mostly engaged in small and medium enterprises (SMEs), in addition to improving product quality and market expansion is also very important to note.

So far, employees of local wisdom products in Palembang are only directed to be able to work from skills that are informally owned and carried out from generation to generation so that the ability of employees to work is still simple or traditional, as the product being seeded, the four local wisdom products in Palembang are only partially able to survive in the local market, although a small portion has penetrated into the international market, such as songket which is in demand in allied countries such as: Malaysia, Brunei Darussalam. Pempek and kerupuk kemplang that have been sold in neighboring countries, while carving cabinets have not entered the international market (DISPERINDAG, 2016).

Matrix of human resource development factor in small and medium enterprise of local wisdom products in Palembang is very necessary for typical regional products in Palembang so that the ability of employees of Pempek, KerupukKemplang, Songket and carving cabinets can continue to be improved so that typical regional products in Palembang can survive and even compete with similar products from domestic and overseas, such as kerupuk kemplang from Taiwanese which are superior in international markets than kerupuk kemplang from Palembang (DISPERINDAG, 2016). This will make local wisdom products in Palembang still not be left even though they have entered various similar products from outside the region and even outside the country.

Matrix of human resource development factors in small and medium enterprises of local wisdom products in Palembang is carried out by analyzing employee knowledge, skills and emotional intelligence so that employees are able to look at regional products on the one hand as well as to maintain the existence of employees working in the small and medium business sector (Hadiyati, 2013) Do not let the local wisdom products produced by the local community disappear drowned out by similar products from outside the region, as happened to Asian products such as tempeh that can be produced by the European community, such as tempe which we can get from Cirebon now. new output tempe from Canada (Mujib, 2013).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

How about Matrix of human resource development factors in small and medium enterprises of local wisdom products in Palembang

LITERATURE REVIEW

The results of the study from EndroSukoco (2015) about the analysis of the influence of ability, skill and emotional intelligence on employee performance at state-owned banks in Kendari. The number of constants (β_0) was -3.250, which meant that if the variable value of knowledge about work, work skills, and emotional intelligence was zero, then the employee's work performance was -3.250. This value indicated that if the employee was not supported by job knowledge, work skills and emotional intelligence in carrying out his / her job, the employee's work performance was negative.

Ability is the capacity of an individual to perform various tasks in a job, including intellectual abilities, the ability of knowledge possessed by a person, physical ability / skills to carry out tasks, the ability of one's emotional intelligence in work (Behling, 2013).

1. Knowledge, Knowledge reflects a person's ability to know, understand, realize and live a task / job that can be developed through formal and non-formal education and experience, (Amstrong, 2013).
2. Skills, Ability to work obtained through formal education or from training, including the ability to determine how to complete a task / job, the ability to determine the best procedure in carrying out a task / job, (Supriyanto, 2013).
3. Emotional intelligence
Related to how a person recognizes his own feelings also towards others that can be a good predictor of the success of one's life (employees) (Hamilton, 2013), the ability to always believe and think positively towards colleagues work, high self-confidence, high desire for achievement, (Agustian, 2014).

Inhibiting factors for human resources development (Zulkarnain, 2013):

1. Lack of relations with outside communities, causing alienated labor and remaining confined to narrow thought patterns.
2. The development of late science and technology is caused by missing information (Fathul, 2013).
3. The attitude of a traditional society, which considers tradition (Hosseini, 2013).
4. Customs or habits, new elements considered as labor can damage the customs or habits that they have long adopted.
5. Dependence, namely the dependence of a community on another party.
6. Superego, which makes it difficult for someone to accept changes (Crump, 2013).
7. Not confident and not safe feeling.

Picture 1
Research design

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was a human resource management research that was planned to be carried out in one year, including: 1. Analyzing of SME employee knowledge included: understanding of the scope of task/job, understanding the procedures for carrying out tasks/work, understanding the way of carrying out tasks/work, appreciation towards task/job responsibilities, understanding of challenges in carrying out tasks/work and the suitability of knowledge possessed with knowledge in carrying out tasks. 2. Analyzing the skills of SME employees including the ability to determine how to complete a task/job, the ability to determine the best procedure in carrying out a task/job, the ability to complete a task well, the ability to determine the best quality of task/job that can be completed and the ability to predict the results of the implementation of the task/job. 3. Analyzing the emotional intelligence of SME employees included the ability to take the initiative, the ability to always believe and think positively of co-workers, high self-confidence, high desire for achievement, the ability to work with colleagues, the ability to control themselves in dealing with constrained task/job problems in Pempek business unit only. This stage was carried out in 2022 starting from December 2021 to March 2022. The output of this research activity was 1. Matrix of human resource development factors in small and medium enterprises of local wisdom products in Palembang. 2. Publication of research results in international journals.

Population And Sample

The population of this study were employees in the typical regional product SMEs in Palembang whose numbers were not known infinite. The sampling technique used purposive sampling technique that was deliberate sampling because it was in accordance with the purpose of the study, in this study the employees in small and medium enterprises of Pempek, located in Tangga Buntung area, Seberang Ulu, Agung Mosque Area, Bukit, in Jenderal Sudirman Street, Basuki rahmat Street, Radial Street, Colonel Iskandar Street and Kapten A Rivai Street.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results
 CFA X1

VARIABLE	S. LOAD	S.LOAD^2	1- S.LOAD^2
X1.1	0,68	0,4624	0,5376
X1.2	0,81	0,6561	0,3439
X1.3	0,84	0,7056	0,2944
X1.4	0,84	0,7056	0,2944
X1.5	0,59	0,3481	0,6519
X1.6	0,66	0,4356	0,5644
X1.7	0,51	0,2601	0,7399
Jumlah	4,93	3,5735	3,4265
JUMLAH^2	24,3049		

CR 0,87644

VE 0,5105

CFA X2

VARIABLE	S. LOAD	S.LOAD^2	1-S.LOAD^2
X2.1	0,72	0,5184	0,4816
X2.2	0,85	0,7225	0,2775
X2.3	0,65	0,4225	0,5775
X2.4	0,75	0,5625	0,4375
X2.5	0,8	0,64	0,36
X2.6	0,71	0,5041	0,4959

X2.7	0,67	0,4489	0,5511
Jumlah	5,15	3,8189	3,1811
JUMLAH^2	26,5225		
CR	0,892905		
VE	0,545557		

CFA X3

VARIABEL	S. LOAD	S.LOAD^2	1- S.LOAD^2
X3.1	0,81	0,6561	0,3439
X3.2	0,87	0,7569	0,2431
X3.3	0,75	0,5625	0,4375

X3.4	0,91	0,8281	0,1719
X3.5	0,64	0,4096	0,5904
X3.6	0,71	0,5041	0,4959
X3.7	0,71	0,5041	0,4959
Jumlah	5,4	4,2214	2,7786
JUMLAH^2	29,16		

CR 0,913002

VE 0,603057

CFA X4

VARIABEL	S. LOAD	S.LOAD^2	1- S.LOAD^2
X4.1	0,79	0,6241	0,3759
X4.2	0,86	0,7396	0,2604
X4.3	0,78	0,6084	0,3916
X4.4	0,88	0,7744	0,2256
X4.5	0,73	0,5329	0,4671
X4.6	0,7	0,49	0,51
X4.7	0,64	0,4096	0,5904
Jumlah	5,38	4,179	2,821
JUMLAH^2	28,9444		
CR	0,911193		
VE	0,597		

CFA Y

VARIABEL	S. LOAD	S.LOAD ²	1- S.LOAD ²
Y.1	0,74	0,5476	0,4524
Y.2	0,82	0,6724	0,3276
Y.3	0,87	0,7569	0,2431
Y.4	0,91	0,8281	0,1719
Y.5	0,88	0,7744	0,2256
Y.6	0,81	0,6561	0,3439
Y.7	0,74	0,5476	0,4524
Jumlah	5,77	4,7831	2,2169
JUMLAH ²	33,2929		
CR	0,937569		
VE	0,6833		

DATA ANALYSIS

Structural Equations

Based on the results of the analysis, the following structural equation was obtained

Sub structural equation

$$X3 = 1.47 * X1 - 0.73 * X2, \text{Errorvar.} = -0.0033, R^2 = 1.01$$

(0.43)	(0.43)	(0.013)
3.43	-1.72	-0.25

$$X4 = 1.78 * X1 - 1.16 * X2, \text{Errorvar.} = 0.018, R^2 = 0.96$$

(0.66)	(0.65)	(0.020)
2.70	-1.77	0.88

Structural equation

$$Y = -0.28 * X3 + 0.60 * X4 + 0.52 * X1 + 0.094 * X2, \text{Errorvar.} = 0.12, R^2 = 0.83$$

(2.02)	(0.93)	(0.93)	(0.022)
-0.14	0.64	0.56	

Discussion

From the above equation, then:

1. Employee development was directly, positively and significantly influenced by employee competencies, while corporate culture variables had no significant effect.
2. Empowerment of employees was directly, positively and significantly affected by the shipping competence, while the corporate culture variable was not significantly influential.
3. Employee job satisfaction was directly influenced by employee empowerment, employee competence, and company culture in a positive and insignificant manner. While employee development variables had a negative and insignificant effect. Indirectly the variables of competence and corporate culture had no effect.

IV. CONCLUSION

Employee development was directly, positively and significantly influenced by employee competencies, while corporate culture variables were not significantly influential, employee empowerment was directly, positively and significantly influenced by shipping competence, while company culture variables were not significantly influential, employee job satisfaction was directly affected by employee empowerment, employee competence, and corporate culture positively and insignificantly. While employee development variables had a negative and insignificant effect. Indirectly the variables of competence and corporate culture had no effect. The government might be more serious in showing partiality in the trade sector of typical regional products in Palembang. The role of government was very necessary, especially in coaching, it needed to be created competitive and comparative advantages that were very potential to be used as a trigger for increased competitiveness, steps to increase employee development both in the field of production and product distribution.

V. RECOMMENDATION

The skills of employees in the use of production technology and more efficient input of raw materials needed to be developed. Institutional factors (foster father, banking and market) that support employee empowerment would need special attention. In addition, in the country need to be followed by the elimination of high cost economy by eliminating inefficiencies, increasing employee job satisfaction through improving employee competencies, implementing corporate culture that supported employee work, developing employee skills and abilities, and empowering employees.

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